

The Changing Face of Marketing: Role of Artificial Intelligence in Shaping Consumer Experience

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Abstract

The human existence has been shaped by numerous discoveries that have benefited and at times even challenged the human race. Humans have excelled in creating things that have challenged its own imagination and hence justified the title of being the most intelligent species. History is testimony to the ways Steam Power, Electricity and Information Technology has impacted the human kind. The next revolution that is taking place, silently but at a rapid pace, is Artificial Intelligence (AI). The late physicist Stephen Hawking said that the success in the field of AI will perhaps be the biggest achievement of the human mind, but also warned of the possibility of the termination of the human race if we lose control.

There are many who believe that the human race will keep control over AI for many years to come and can reap significant benefits from the use of it. There are also significant others who are skeptical about the coexistence of the creator and its creation. Irrespective of the opposite schools of thought, AI has already started making significant impact on various aspects of life and is on its way to perhaps become the biggest disruption. We have witnessed so far. The aim of this paper is to trace the evolution of AI and look at the ways it's impacting the field of Marketing. The authors look to present a layman's understanding about AI's role in marketing and perhaps throw light on its probable future applications without inclining towards any particular school of thought.

Keywords: AI, Evolution, Technology, Marketing, Consumer Engagement, Experience

Introduction

What is Artificial Intelligence?

Artificial can refer to anything that is not real; it is something that's fake because it is simulated essentially. Intelligence however is a more complex term. It can be things such as logic, understanding, problem solving, creativity, etc. We call humans intelligent because they exhibit the traits mentioned and we can say the same about plants and animals. Now machines, computers, and robots are said to have “Artificial” intelligence as they mimic or simulate the

intelligence that we human beings possess. AI has been prevalent in several works of fiction and imagination throughout the years.

Artificial intelligence was a discipline founded in 1956 and was followed by huge waves of optimism and funding and then a stagnation period known as the AI Winter. Recently however AI has picked up again and has been making great sides.

Artificial intelligence has had big impacts on the human race as a whole from increasing workforce efficiency to making our lives easier and more comfortable.

In just the 2000's itself there have been several notable events that have been great leaps in the field of AI

In the year 2000 we saw expressive robots such as "Kismet" capable of facial expressions just like human beings. The Nomad robot too was unveiled which scoured Antarctica looking for meteorite samples.

In 2002 iRobots Roomba was introduced. The first robot to enter the household. It could autonomously vacuum floors and avoid obstacles.

In 2004 NASA's robotic exploration rovers Spirit and Opportunity autonomously navigated the surface of Mars.

In 2005 we had Honda's Asimo robot which could move just like a human being delivering trays to customers in restaurants. Recommendation technology too came into the foray and we saw Tivo providing show recommendations to customers thus AI entered the field of marketing.

In 2007 we scientists in the University of Alberta taught AI to play checkers and DARPA launched the Urban Challenge for autonomous cars to obey traffic rules and operate in an urban environment.

And in 2009 Google built the first autonomous car

In 2010 Microsoft launched the Xbox Kinect which could track human movement. It was a very successful motion tracking project.

In 2011 IBM's Watson computer defeated television game show Jeopardy! Champions Rutter and Jennings.

From 2011-14 we saw that AI assistants like Siri, Cortana, and Google Now came into the picture.

In 2015 an open letter to ban development and use of autonomous weapons was signed by Hawking, Musk, Wozniak and 3,000 researchers in AI and robotics and Google's DeepmindAlphaGo bot beat the best in the game.

In 2017 AI learned to play an even more complex video game Dota2 and beat a leading champion in a 1v1 game and an even more advanced version of the bot that beat ranked players in Go was released.

In 2018 AI again beat humans. Alibaba language processing AI outscored top humans at a Stanford University reading and comprehension test and finally Google Duplex was launched an AI assistant that could book appointments over the phone. It is nearly flawless and indistinguishable from human speech.

Implications of artificial intelligence on businesses

Artificial Intelligence is the future and it is here to stay but what implications does the growth of Artificial Intelligence have on businesses?

Several authors together including Mike Baccala, Chris Curran, Dan Garrett, Scott Likens, Anand Rao, Andy Ruggles, Michael Shahabad several other contributors have made some bold predictions in a paper named "2018 AI predictions 8 insights to shape business strategy"

The authors claim that Artificial Intelligence will affect employers long before they will affect

employees. Artificial Intelligence and human beings will in most cases work in tandem with each other and not against each other. This fact is enumerated with the example of high level chess players being beat not solely by Artificial Intelligence programs but by “Centaur” i.e. a combination of efforts between AI and humans where decisions made by the AI are free to be overridden and analysed by the human being anytime.

AI will eliminate the need for menial and repetitive tasks in several industries and economies. This however will also allow individuals to focus on more pressing and important work. Even then in PwC’s forthcoming international jobs automation study, due in February 2018, it is estimated that across 29 countries analyzed, the share of jobs at potential high risk of automation is only 1 percent by 2020.

Employees in this new day and age will not only need how to choose correct algorithms and how to feed data into AI programs but it is also essential that they understand how to interpret results and come to conclusions. AI will also change how the employees work in teams. Different departments will be required to work together in close collaboration with each other to solve problems and later monitor the results.

67% of executives have said that AI will help humans and machines work together to be stronger using both artificial and human intelligence. (PwC Consumer Intelligence Series: Bot.Me, 2017 Base: 500 business executives)

54 % of business executives say AI solutions implemented in their businesses have already increased productivity (PwC Consumer Intelligence Series: Bot.Me, 2017)

One area that AI already shows superiority over human beings is hacking and we will see in the future that AI will be a very powerful cyber threat as well as a powerful cyber defence.

Already, scalable machine learning techniques combined with cloud technology are analyzing enormous amount of data and powering real-time threat detection and analysis. AI capabilities can also quickly identify “hot spots” where cyberattacks are surging and provide cybersecurity intelligence reports.

The winner of the US Defense Department’s DARPA Cyber Grand Challenge, a cybersecurity competition, used AI deep learning—and the Pentagon has purchased the technology.

Even then humans are better at some tasks than AI such as absorbing context and thinking imaginatively and will stay play big roles in preventing and protecting against cyber threats.

We will see in the future that perhaps this potential threat from AI will help speed up the process of acceptance of AI by organisations as they are a highly potent defence. We will see organisations investing and taking up AI to protect them and help them perform better.

27 % of executives say their organization plans to invest this year in cybersecurity safeguards that use AI and machine learning (PwC 2018 Global State of Information Security® Survey Base: 9.500 business and technology executives)

We will also see in the future there will be a great need for accountability, explain ability , and provability. Therefore Opening black boxes will reduce certain risks and help establish stakeholder trust. Transparency is essential.

Implications of Artificial Intelligence on Marketing

Artificial Intelligence can help with marketing and digital commerce and has several benefits including increased accuracy, improved efficiency, more granularity in analysis and orchestration, the ability to deal with large amounts of data with different attributes, and even frequent algorithm refreshes to capture transient changes in customer and market behavior. It should also be noted that although AI can help with all these things it should not be misunderstood that AI can solve all problems and is a cure all.

Now here are the ways in which AI can help assist in marketing and digital commerce operations- Businesses can personalize their interactions with customers using data collected by presenting the right contents and formats. With AI personalization engines can quickly discover the correlation between customers attributes and observed activities. AI then can provide content from several different sources factoring in large number of attributes to truly provide a proper personal experience.

There are several ways in which AI can provide a personal touch

AI making use of data provided can be frequently tested and improved to provide customers proper product recommendations based on several attributes such as demography, behavior, preferences, etc and can continually learn and improve. AI can factor in multiple data sources to understand consumer behavior and provide a much better search experience. Thus helping business increase the conversion rates. Solid Signal for example by incorporating this technology doubled its conversion rate to 6% and minimized its exit rate by 33.5%.

AI can even gather information about a consumer and provide the appropriate landing page for them to ensure that the best impact is made on them. AI can even help make some tasks easier. AI can group different products based on their attributes and characteristics and since AI can access huge amounts of data it can be very proficient in demand forecasting.

Furthermore, AI can effectively identify fraud much faster than rule engines eliminating that threat and thus helping out managers. Another way AI can help is with Inventory management. AI can understand the ideal location, stock availability, distance from customer, and other such factors and help with efficient and effective inventory management. By considering a wide variety of factors such as cost, inventory, margin, etc AI can provide dynamic pricing too and by analyzing consumer behavior AI can identify those consumers who will be more responsive to loyalty programs, marketing schemes, etc.

Conclusion

AI will have a huge impact on the way we live our lives. Each and every routine task will be integrated with this new technology. Business and industries need to realize the need and benefits of AI and should start planning to adapt it for sustain in the future market. But over reliance on technology, people could become disconnected from the process and cease to understand how things work. Also AI is going to bestow success to the business, with better understanding of customers and relation with them. However more than replacing humans, a combination of AI and humans is more going to benefit the business.

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